

Research Libraries Powering sustainable Knowledge in the Digital Age: LIBER's Open Science Strategy

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*Jeannette Frey, LIBER President
Director, BCU Lausanne*

EUROPE'S RESEARCH LIBRARY NETWORK

Founded in 1971

Research libraries working together for nearly 50 years

470 Libraries

National and university libraries, plus special libraries, consortia and individuals

40 Countries

One third of LIBER libraries are located in southern and eastern Europe

VISION: THE 2022 RESEARCH LANDSCAPE

Open Access

The main form of publishing

Research Infrastructure

Participatory, tailored and scaled to the needs of diverse disciplines

Research Data

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)

Cultural Heritage

Tomorrow's cultural heritage built on today's digital information

Digital Skills

Underpinning a more open, transparent research life cycle

POWERING SUSTAINABLE KNOWLEDGE IN THE DIGITAL AGE

STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS and WORKING GROUPS

LIBRARIES AS A PLATFORM FOR INNOVATIVE COMMUNICATION

LIBRARIES PARTNERING IN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

LIBRARIES AS A HUB FOR DIGITAL SKILLS AND SERVICES

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LIBER RESOURCES & GUIDANCE FOR MEMBERS

Alerting our network to top trends and issues through reports, factsheets and other resources.

www.libereurope.eu/resources

3. Service Development

These recommendations focus on service development by reusing existing services and tools and returning them to the community of academic libraries. Reuse and mash-ups of tools, data, methods, and services, as well as standardization and interoperability are critical for ensuring the provision of responsible services around scholarly metrics. This enables tailoring services to the needs of academic libraries and increases the reusability of services and tools. This is especially important for small and medium-sized libraries that lack manpower and are therefore the main beneficiary of collaborative and open service development.

3A. JOIN FORCES WITH STAKEHOLDERS TO PROVIDE SERVICES REUSING EXISTING RESOURCES, TOOLS, METHODS & DATA

- Start with enriching existing sources and databases at your library (e.g., add scholarly metrics to the CRIS and/or institutional repository).¹⁰ Learn about scholarly metrics via any possible means including librquides, schools and product training.¹¹ Provide information about the tasks and how to perform them (e.g., via websites, trainings). Provide tools for

3B. VALUE VARIOUS LEVELS OF ENGAGEMENT; FAVOUR STANDARDIZED, WELL-ESTABLISHED PRACTICES & EASY-TO-USE TOOLS

- Find and define tasks that researchers can do by themselves, such as updating user profiles on social media platforms. (Do it Yourself-level of engagement). Provide information about the tasks and how to perform them (e.g., via websites, trainings). Provide tools for

TDM EXCEPTION

FOUR ESSENTIAL POINTS FOR COPYRIGHT REFORM

On behalf of our open European research libraries, LIBER is calling for four essential points to be included in any Text and Data Mining (TDM) Exception proposed by the European Commission as part of its copyright overhaul for the Digital Single Market. These points must be addressed if a TDM Exception is to be effective for Europe's research community.

1. MAKE THE TDM EXCEPTION MANDATORY & NON-OVERRIDABLE

Such provisions are already included in the Commission's proposal (Article 17, 18 and 19) and in the draft DSM report. We welcome this approach. The Commission's proposal, Article 17, allows rightsholders to apply measures to ensure the security and integrity of the networks and databases. A clarification is needed that technical measures may not be used to prevent beneficiaries from exercising their rights under an exception, or to impose unreasonable limitations on how TDM is performed.

2. INCLUDE LIBRARIES & ALL PERSONS WITH LAWFUL ACCESS TO CONTENT AS BENEFICIARIES

The beneficiaries of the TDM exception should be extended to include all 'persons' with lawful access so as to benefit citizen science, historians, the research community, journalism and other actors of society and the economy. The right to read should be the right to mine.

3. ALLOW COMMERCIAL & NON-COMMERCIAL USES, WITHOUT COMPENSATION

Since TDM is only used to extract facts and data, which are not copyrightable, it is reasonable to limit TDM to non-commercial purposes. The copy of the content being re-used or communicated to the public. Researchers should be able to use the facts and figures in a larger context.¹²

What is FAIR DATA?

<p>Data and supplementary materials have sufficiently rich metadata and a unique and persistent identifier.</p> <p>FINDABLE</p>	<p>Metadata and data are understandable to humans and machines. Data is deposited in a trusted repository.</p> <p>ACCESSIBLE</p>
<p>Metadata use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>INTEROPERABLE</p>	<p>Data and collections have a clear usage licenses and provide accurate information on provenance.</p> <p>REUSABLE</p>

Why is FAIR Data important?

The development of digital science thrives on the timely sharing and accessibility of data. The development of infrastructures and services that support the transition to Open Science is now strongly advocated. FAIR principles strengthen them.

LIBER RESOURCES: Scholarly Metrics Recommendations

Discovery and Discoverability

Showcasing Achievements

Service development

Research Assessment

LIBER RESOURCES: Webinars

GDPR – What Does It Mean For
Researchers?

Turning FAIR Data Into Reality

EU Copyright Reform & Why Research
Libraries Should Care

TU Delft's Data Stewardship project

OPEN SCIENCE ROADMAP

Translates Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP) advice for libraries.

Adds suggestions drawn from the experiences of LIBER institutions.

Over 1000 downloads!

<https://zenodo.org/record/1303002>

CURRENT WORK

LIBER
Open Science
Roadmap

Plan S

cOAlition S
**Making
Open Access
a reality
by 2020**

A DECLARATION OF COMMITMENT
BY PUBLIC RESEARCH FUNDERS

<http://scieur.org/coalition>

"After 1 January 2020 scientific publications on the results from research funded by public grants provided by national and European research councils and funding bodies, must be published in compliant Open Access Journals or on compliant Open Access Platforms."

In addition:

01 Authors retain copyright of their publication with no restrictions. All publications must be published under an open license, preferably the Creative Commons Attribution Licence CC BY. In all cases, the license applied should fulfil the requirements defined by the Berlin Declaration;

02 The Funders will ensure jointly the establishment of robust criteria and requirements for the services that compliant high quality Open Access journals and Open Access platforms must provide;

03 In case such high quality Open Access journals or platforms do not yet exist, the Funders will, in a coordinated way, provide incentives to establish and support them when appropriate; support will also be provided for Open Access infrastructures where necessary;

04 Where applicable, Open Access publication fees are covered by the Funders or universities, not by individual researchers; it is acknowledged that all scientists should be able to publish their work Open Access even if their institutions have limited means;

05 When Open Access publication fees are applied, their funding is standardised and capped (across Europe);

06 The Funders will ask universities, research organisations, and libraries to align their policies and strategies, notably to ensure transparency;

07 The above principles shall apply to all types of scholarly publications, but it is understood that the timeline to achieve Open Access for monographs and books may be longer than 1 January 2020;

08 The importance of open archives and repositories for hosting research outputs is acknowledged because of their long-term archiving function and their potential for editorial innovation;

09 The 'hybrid' model of publishing is not compliant with the above principles;

10 The Funders will monitor compliance and sanction non-compliance.

Capture d'écran

LIBER OA Working group Recommandation on Plan S

LIBER OPEN ACCESS WORKING GROUP
WORKED ON THE ANALYSIS OF THE UPDATED
IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

- **RELIEVED PRESSURE ON TECHNICAL PLATFORMS**
- **ALIGNMENT** WITH DoRA, OA2020, ESAC GUIDELINES
- **SUPPORT A DIVERSITY OF BUSINESS MODELS**
- **TRANSPARENCY OF COSTS IS KEY**

LIBER Status on Plan S

LIBRARIES CAN WORK ON **ALIGNMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORIES**

PLAN S ASKS FOR FULL TRANSPARENCY OF COSTS: STILL LOTS OF WORK TO DO

DIGITIZED COLLECTION: USE CC-BY LICENCES

BE INVOLVED IN **LONG TERM PRESERVATION**

SUPPORT IMPLEMENTATION AND USE OF **IDENTIFIERS**

COMPLIANCE WITH OPENAIRE

HORIZON EUROPE

HORIZON EUROPE: 2021-2027

100 BILLION EURO

»MISSIONS«

LIBER and HORIZON EUROPE

HORIZON-EUROPE CO-DESIGN 2021-2024

- SEPTEMBER 15, 2019,
CONSULTATION
- LIBER ANSWERED THE
CONSULTATION

LOOKING FORWARD..

Ideas, suggestions, questions:

- liber@kb.nl
- Jeannette.frey@bcu.unil.ch
- @LIBEReurope

www.libereurope.eu/

JOIN A WORKING GROUP

Broaden your network.

Share knowledge.

**Everyone working in a LIBER library is
welcome!**

THANKS!

Questions?

Jeannette.frey@bcu.unil.ch